

Appendix A: Tables

This appendix section includes tables describing the sample and their properties. Table A.1 gives the target list with information from the literature and catalogs. Table A.2 provides information for the mass ejection events that were sampled in this work, including the emission asymmetry frequencies. Table A.3 includes stellar properties and the orbital, critical, and rotational frequencies as derived from (Zorec et al. 2016), and Tbl. A.4 lists the observing log.

Table A.1. Target list.

ID	HD	TESS ID	Spectral Type	Vmag	$v \sin i$ (km s ⁻¹)	i (°)
This work						
V767 Cen	120991	307225534	B2Ve	6.1	106 ± 11 (1)	25° ± 7° (1)
f Car	75311	46028220	B3Vne	4.49	268 ± 18 (1)	66° ± 16° (1)
12 Vul	187811	299630806	B2.5Ve	4.96	264 ± 25 (1)	52° ± 13° (1)
						60° ± 5° (2)
V442 And	6226	196501216	B2.5IIIe	6.82	57 ⁺⁴² ₋₁₈ (3)	13.4 ^{+2.5} _{-3.0} (3)
λ Pav	173948	375232307	B2Ve	4.21	145 ± 12 (1)	36° ± 10° (1)
					130 ± 15 (5)	
ι Lyr	178475	120967488	B6IVe	5.25	...	intermediate/high
28 Cyg	191610	42360166	B2.5Ve	4.93	314 ± 33 (1)	69° ± 17° (1)
						40° ± 5° (2)
V357 Lac	212044	431116093	B2e	6.98	...	low
OT Gem	58050	14498757	B2Ve	6.41	138 ± 12 (1)	31° ± 12° (1)
						21° ± 6° (2)
25 Ori	35439	264459943	B1Vne	4.96	284 ± 28 (1)	58° ± 14° (1)
						63° ± 5° (2)
						55° ± 5° (4)
κ CMa	50013	52982382	B1.5Ve	3.89	231 ± 25 (1)	50° ± 17° (1)
						57° ± 13° (2)
						53° ± 10° (4)
j Cen	102776	325170579	B3Ve	4.31	...	intermediate
120 Tau	36576	437790952	B2IV-Ve	5.69	282 ± 29 (1)	57° ± 14° (1)
						61° ± 9° (2)
						60° ± 5° (4)
Literature sample						
μ Cen	120324	243647020	B2Vnpe	3.43	149 ± 13 (1)	30° ± 11° (1); 38° ± 11° (2)
ω CMa	56139	65903024	B2.5Ve	3.82	94 ± 13 (1)	24° ± 8° (1); 37° ± 5° (2)
ω Ori	37490	281047621	B3Ve	4.59	190 ± 21 (1)	50° ± 12° (1); 59° ± 10° (2)
ν Cyg	202904	117146835	B2Vne	4.42	193 ± 23 (1)	38° ± 9° (1); 50° ± 13° (2)
EW Lac	217050	252500679	B4IIIpe	5.43	358 ± 37 (1)	72° ± 18° (1)
η Cen	127972	128116539	B2Ve	2.31	328 ± 33 (1)	67° ± 16° (1); 77° ± 5° (2)

Notes. References for $v \sin i$ and i are given in parenthesis. For stars without numerical inclination angles, the inclination is qualitatively described based on the emission line morphology.

References. (1) Zorec et al. (2016); (2) Sigut & Ghafourian (2023); (3) Richardson et al. (2021); (4) Cochetti et al. (2019); (5) Levenhagen et al. (2011).

Table A.2. Information about the well-sampled flickers.

ID	Flicker types	Em. osc. freq (d ⁻¹)	Method	Num. Cycles	t _b /t _d (d)	Amp. (% flx)	Spec puls freq (d ⁻¹)
This work							
V767 Cen	Clear	0.773 ± 0.025	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	3*	4.3/...	7.5	0.97867
	Clear	0.865 ± 0.012	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	7	9.3/...	14.9	
f Car	Pristine	1.674 ± 0.036	H α EW _V /EW _R	5	0.9/3.1	1.8	2.0898, 3.7520, 3.8370
	Pristine	1.722 ± 0.032	H α EW _V /EW _R	6	2.5/4.7	8.3	
12 Vul	Complex	1.765 ± 0.083	H α EW _V /EW _R	2*	1.3/...	3.4	2.0158, 2.1077
	Complex	1.916 ± 0.069	H α EW _V /EW _R	4	2.1/...	4.8	
	Complex	1.60 ± 0.15	H α EW _V /EW _R	1**	
V442 And	Pristine	0.348 ± 0.007	H α EW _V /EW _R	6	0.382332 (11)
	Pristine	0.353 ± 0.004	H α EW _V /EW _R	9	
	Clear	0.358 ± 0.005	H α EW _V /EW _R	9	
	Pristine	0.356 ± 0.004	H α EW _V /EW _R	10	
	Clear	0.351 ± 0.004	H α EW _V /EW _R	10	
	Pristine	0.352 ± 0.007	H α EW _V /EW _R	6	
	Pristine	0.362 ± 0.005	H α EW _V /EW _R	10	10.7/...	4.4	
	Pristine	0.332 ± 0.009	H α EW _V /EW _R	4	
	Pristine	0.341 ± 0.005	H α EW _V /EW _R	9	
λ Pav	Pristine	0.810 ± 0.014	H α EW _V /EW _R	7**	0.49, 0.82, 1.63 (12)
ι Lyr	Pristine	0.983 ± 0.016	H α EW _V /EW _R	6	
28 Cyg	Clear	1.415 ± 0.049	H α EW _V /EW _R	3	2.0/7.5	5.7	1.54562, 1.59726 (13)
V357 Lac	Clear	1.085 ± 0.033	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	6*	
	Complex	1.092 ± 0.062	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	4**	3.0/...	10.5	
	Clear	1.165 ± 0.028	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	5**	4.3/...	17.5	
OT Gem	Clear	2.161 ± 0.025	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	9	7.6/...	20.0	2.494
	Clear	2.000 ± 0.029	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	6**	1.6/...	1.2	
	Clear	2.086 ± 0.034	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	9	4.9/3.9	13.0	
25 Ori	Complex	1.568 ± 0.049	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	3.5	1.6793
	Complex	1.565 ± 0.047	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	3.5**	
κ CMa	Complex	1.546 ± 0.020	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	8	1.8256
	Complex	1.480 ± 0.022	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	6	
j Cen	Complex	1.719 ± 0.016	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	12?	1.9650
120 Tau	Complex	0.966 ± 0.016	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	7	1.2400
	Complex	1.048 ± 0.022	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	5*	
	Complex	0.975 ± 0.024	H α wings EW _V /EW _R	5**	
From the literature							
μ Cen	...	1.608 ± 0.013 (1)	He I V/R	1.98837, 1.97037, 2.02215 (2)
	...	1.686 ± 0.026 (1)	He I V/R	3.55360, 3.58247 (2)
	...	1.72 (1)	H β V/R	
	...	1.4 (1)	He I λ 6678 V/R	
ω CMa	...	0.680 (3)	Fe II lines V/R	0.7289 (4)
ω Ori	...	0.46 (5)	He I λ 5876, 6678 V/R	1.03 (5)
ν Cyg	...	1.5 (6)	He I λ 6678 V/R	2.95, 2.6 (6)
EW Lac	...	1.22 (7)	He I λ 6678 V/R	1.39, 1.55, 2.76 (7)
η Cen	...	1.56 (8,9)	Si III λ 4553	1.75 (8,9)
	...	0.61 (10)	He I, Fe II, Mg II, Si II	1.48, 3.81, 5.31 (10)

Notes. The columns are as follows. *Flicker types*: ‘Pristine’ refers to events where there was no pre-existing disk. ‘Clear’ indicates flickers where there was a pre-existing disk but the flicker is well defined. ‘Complex’ refers to mass ejections where it is difficult to determine exactly when events start and/or end. *Em. osc. freq*: The frequency of the emission asymmetry oscillations. *Method*: The method used to measure the emission asymmetry oscillations, where ‘H α EW_V/EW_R’ made use of the full line profile and ‘H α wings EW_V/EW_R’ used just the high-velocity emission wings. *Num. Cycles*: The approximate number of emission asymmetry cycles sampled by the data for a given event. The superscript * indicates that the event was interrupted by another event, and ** indicates a gap in observations (i.e., the reported cycle numbers are a lower limit). *t_b/t_d*: The build-up and dissipation times from TESS for isolated and well-defined flickers are given in days whenever it was possible to measure these quantities. *Amp.*: The maximum photometric amplitude of the flicker whenever measurements were possible. *Spec puls freq*: Spectroscopic pulsation frequencies determined from absorption line profile variations. Each row corresponds to a different flicker event. References for quantities from the literature are given in parenthesis.

References. (1) Rivinius et al. (1998b); (2) Rivinius et al. (1998c); (3) Štefl et al. (2003a); (4) Štefl et al. (2003b); (5) Neiner et al. (2002); (6) Neiner et al. (2005); (7) Floquet et al. (2000); (8) Štefl et al. (1998); (9) Štefl et al. (1995); (10) Levenhagen et al. (2003); (11) Richardson et al. (2021); (12) Levenhagen et al. (2011); (13) Tubbesing et al. (2000).

Table A.3. Fundamental parameters and frequencies computed for the stars in Tab. A.1 with corresponding data in Zorec et al. (2016).

ID	Mass (M_{\odot})	R_e (R_{\odot})	R_p (R_{\odot})	f_{orb} (d^{-1})	f_{crit} (d^{-1})	f_{rot} (d^{-1})
V767 Cen	18.0 ± 2.5	12.3 ± 2.7	10.5 ± 2.2	0.85 ± 0.22	0.58 ± 0.14	0.40 ± 0.14
f Car	7.60 ± 0.30	5.8 ± 1.3	4.6 ± 1.0	1.71 ± 0.43	1.33 ± 0.33	1.11 ± 0.30
12 Vul	8.10 ± 0.30	5.3 ± 1.9	4.3 ± 1.5	2.02 ± 0.79	1.47 ± 0.57	1.25 ± 0.51
λ Pav	12.90 ± 0.80	10.7 ± 2.2	9.0 ± 1.8	0.88 ± 0.21	0.62 ± 0.14	0.46 ± 0.15
28 Cyg	10.50 ± 0.50	7.7 ± 1.7	6.1 ± 1.3	1.31 ± 0.33	1.01 ± 0.25	0.86 ± 0.24
OT Gem	10.70 ± 0.80	6.3 ± 1.1	5.2 ± 0.9	1.78 ± 0.36	1.28 ± 0.24	0.84 ± 0.34
25 Ori	12.80 ± 0.90	8.1 ± 1.9	6.6 ± 1.5	1.33 ± 0.36	0.98 ± 0.26	0.81 ± 0.24
κ CMa	13.1 ± 2.9	4.8 ± 2.9	4.3 ± 2.6	2.96 ± 2.02	1.91 ± 1.29	1.24 ± 0.82
120 Tau	15.5 ± 1.0	8.9 ± 2.0	7.2 ± 1.6	1.27 ± 0.32	0.95 ± 0.24	0.74 ± 0.22
μ Cen	10.8 ± 1.3	5.3 ± 2.6	4.5 ± 2.2	2.30 ± 1.24	1.60 ± 0.86	1.10 ± 0.65
ω CMa	9.90 ± 0.20	9.0 ± 4.6	7.6 ± 3.9	1.00 ± 0.57	0.70 ± 0.40	0.51 ± 0.31
ω Ori	11.10 ± 0.70	12.7 ± 3.7	10.4 ± 3.0	0.63 ± 0.21	0.47 ± 0.15	0.39 ± 0.14
ν Cyg	9.50 ± 0.50	5.8 ± 1.9	4.8 ± 1.6	1.91 ± 0.71	1.37 ± 0.50	1.07 ± 0.43
EW Lac	8.80 ± 0.60	7.2 ± 3.1	5.6 ± 2.4	1.31 ± 0.63	1.04 ± 0.50	1.03 ± 0.47
η Cen	10.20 ± 0.50	6.2 ± 1.5	4.9 ± 1.1	1.77 ± 0.47	1.37 ± 0.36	1.13 ± 0.32

Table A.4. Observing log.

ID	Num. spectra during TESS	TESS Sec.	Num. spectra total	Date range total (TJD)
V767 Cen	249 (N), 23 (B)	64, 65	293 (N), 26 (B)	3025 – 3115
f Car	225 (N)	62, 63	236 (N)	2979 – 3043
12 Vul	323 (N), 27 (D), 53 (B)	54	364 (N), 68 (D), 94 (B)	2745 – 2807
V442 And	6 (N), 321 (B)	17, 57, 58	6 (N), 1217 (B)	956 – 3374
λ Pav	136 (N), 262 (C)	67	154 (N), 518 (C)	3101 – 3196
ι Lyr	48 (N), 63 (D), 55 (B)	53, 54	51 (N), 72 (D), 59 (B)	2713 – 2802
28 Cyg	83 (N), 63 (B)	54, 55	83 (N), 14 (D), 64 (B)	2708 – 2825
V357 Lac	24 (N), 83 (B)	16, 17	24 (N), 98 (B)	1700 – 1850
OT Gem	133 (N)	71, 72	137 (N)	3235 – 3294
25 Ori	170 (N)	32	198 (N)	2096 – 2237
κ CMa	279 (N)	33, 34	289 (N)	2197 – 2246
j Cen	157 (N)	37, 38	179 (N)	2285 – 2362
120 Tau	130 (N)	44, 45	142 (N)	2487 – 2552

Notes. The second column lists the number of spectra taken during the relevant TESS sectors, printed in the third column. The letters in parenthesis after the number of spectra indicate the source of the spectra: N = NRES, B = BeSS, D = DAO, and C = CHIRON. The number of spectra total, in the fourth column, give the quantity of observations surrounding and including the dates of the TESS observations, corresponding to the date range total given in the last column. For V442 And, the number of spectra in the ‘TESS’ column corresponds to the spectra used to measure the EW_V/EW_R frequencies in the nine events shown in Fig. B.1, and the number in the next column is the total number of observations as shown in the top two panels of Fig. B.1. The TESS sectors (<https://tess.mit.edu/observations/>) are those used in this study with contemporaneous spectroscopy, but additional TESS data are available for all targets.

Appendix C: Flickers at low inclination angles

Two Be stars at low inclination angles, HD 35345 and PQ Pup, are briefly discussed to emphasize the increase in brightness oscillations that often coincide with mass ejection. The photometric behavior is qualitatively the same as in the higher inclination angle cases, but the increase in power of the frequency groups can be much more stark, and there should be no obscuration of the star due to ejected material. Although there do not seem to be measurements of the inclination angle in the literature for either system, they are certainly low based on the emission line morphology and narrowness of photospheric absorption lines. These examples bolster the argument that the enhancement in photometric frequency groups during outburst are at least partially photospheric (Sect. 5.4).

Due to geometric cancellation, the photometric amplitude of sectoral modes ($l = |m|$) decreases with decreasing inclination. The much higher amplitude signals that emerge during outburst may be of a different nature than the ‘standard’ sectoral modes commonly observed in Be stars.

Appendix C.1: HD 35345 (B1Vpe)

This system experienced frequent, high-amplitude, short-lived flickers in nine years of ground-based KELT photometry and in all spectroscopic observations displayed strong single-peaked emission lines with $H\alpha$ reaching up to ~ 10 times the continuum level (Labadie-Bartz et al. 2018, their Fig. 25). TESS observed HD 35345 in sectors 43 and 44. For the first ~ 35 days of these observations, the system exhibited typical low-amplitude variability. The last ~ 15 days saw the system brighten by about 45%, with a significant increase in amplitude of the photometric oscillations. Fig. C.1 shows the TESS light curve, and the frequency spectrum computed from the pre-outburst data (prior to TJD 2510) and the in-outburst data (after TJD 2510). The amplitude of signals in the $g1$ frequency group increased by a factor of about 30, and in $g2$ by a factor of about 4.

One NRES spectrum was acquired at the beginning of the event at TJD 2512, and a second and third 12 and 18 days later, respectively (right panels of Fig. C.1). In the first spectrum, high-velocity asymmetric emission is strongly detected in $He\ I$ lines, consistent with asymmetric mass ejection.

Fig. C.1. Photometric and spectroscopic information for HD 35345. The top left panel shows the TESS light curve from sectors 43 and 44 (black), with a fit to the low frequency variation (purple). Subtracting this fit results in the flattened light curve (plus a vertical offset, grey points). The middle left panel shows the frequency spectrum computed from the pre-outburst data, prior to TJD 2510 (the grey curve is computed from the original data, and black from the flattened light curve). The bottom panel shows the frequency spectrum of the in-outburst data (red, after TJD 2510) compared to the pre-outburst data (black). The right panels show three NRES epochs for $H\alpha$, $H\gamma$, and $He\ I\ \lambda 5877$. The line color and style corresponds to the observation date (matching the vertical lines in the top-left panel).

Appendix C.2: PQ Pup (B3Ve)

TESS observations of this star in sectors 34 and 35 showed a high-amplitude ($\sim 20\%$) outburst also with a strong increase in amplitude of the more rapid oscillations. TESS observations in sectors 61 and 62 did not show any sign of mass ejection, although low-level relatively slow variations are present in addition to the typical frequency groups. The frequency spectrum computed from the sector 61 and 62 data is compared to the frequency spectrum computed from the in-outburst data (after TJD 2241 in sectors 34 and 35). The strongest signal in the $g1$ frequency group increased by a factor of 5, and in the second $g2$ group by a factor of 40.

Unfortunately, no spectroscopy is available during the outburst in sectors 34 and 35. We acquired 16 NRES spectra during sectors 61 and 62, with observing dates indicated by the tick marks in the top panel of Fig. C.2 and selected corresponding line profiles in the right panels. During this time, the strength of emission lines was slightly decreasing, consistent with a dissipating disk without being replenished by new mass ejection. The line profile variations in e.g., $He\ I\ \lambda 5877$ are consistent with pulsation.

Fig. C.2. Similar to Fig. C.1 but for PQ Pup. The top-left panel shows the TESS photometry while the star was apparently not ejecting material. The second-left panel is plotted in the same style as the top panel in Fig. C.1. The third-left panel shows the frequency spectrum from the sector 61 and 62 data, and the bottom-left panel adds the frequency spectrum from the sector 34 and 35 data (after TJD 2241). The tick marks in the top panel are the NRES epochs plotted in the right panels (no spectroscopy is available during sectors 34 and 35).

Appendix D: μ Cen, η Cen, and ω CMa – TESS photometry and archival spectra

TESS has observed μ Cen in three sectors, as shown in Fig. D.1. As a well known highly active star, it is no surprise that several flickers were recorded by TESS. However, contemporaneous spectroscopy is not available for this system. In the highest amplitude event (sector 11), the brightness increased by about 23%. The photometric frequency groups are wide and variable. The spectroscopic pulsation frequencies from Rivinius et al. (1998c) (vertical blue dotted lines in Fig. D.1) do not obviously stand out in the photometry. In TESS photometry, and considering previous spectroscopic studies (Hanuschik et al. 1993; Rivinius et al. 1998b), the behavior of μ Cen on short timescales is similar to the 13 star sample studied in this work.

Fig. D.1. Available TESS data for μ Cen from sectors 11, 38, and 64. The lighter grey curve describes the low-frequency variability, which was subtracted prior to the calculation of the frequency spectra in the bottom panel. The red and blue vertical lines in the bottom panel are the V/R and spectroscopic pulsation frequencies, respectively.

η Cen and ω CMa are noteworthy for their long-lasting quasi-permanent Štefl frequencies (Rivinius et al. 2003; Baade et al. 2016; Štefl et al. 2003b). These frequencies (and/or phases) do slightly change over time, and the amplitude of the associated V/R (or EW_V/EW_R) oscillations vary. Nevertheless, the persistence of the Štefl frequencies in η Cen and ω CMa distinguish them from the sample introduced in this work whose Štefl frequencies appear suddenly and typically persist for only several oscillation cycles.

Figure D.2 plots the available TESS photometry and its frequency content for η Cen and ω CMa, respectively. For η Cen, TESS does not record any short-lived flickers. The variations in the three available TESS sectors are all very similar to each other, and also to the BRITE photometry presented in Baade et al. (2016). The dominant signal in photometry corresponds to the spectroscopic Štefl frequency, and there is a fairly strong signal at 0.033 d^{-1} in good agreement with BRITE (but with poor frequency resolution). There are additionally several lower-amplitude signals in/near the two main photometric frequency groups. In the TESS photometry for ω CMa, slow, apparently oscillatory, variations dominant the light curves. Without contemporaneous spectroscopy, it is difficult to determine if these slow variations are associated with disk-build up or are photospheric. Out of the four available TESS sectors, sector 7 exhibits relatively high amplitude frequency groups (possibly hinting at ongoing or enhanced mass loss), whereas the other three sectors are all similar to each other. There does appear to be a photometric signal in TESS associated with the Štefl frequency, but it does not dominate the frequency spectrum as in η Cen.

Figures D.3 and D.4 show archival $H\alpha$ data from the Heidelberg Extended Range Optical Spectrograph (HEROS) for η Cen and ω CMa, respectively. The $H\alpha$ spectra start in January 1996, and extend to June 1996 (η Cen) and March 1996 (ω CMa). Both stars had a fairly strong disk during these timespans. η Cen is a shell star, and exhibited variations in its $H\alpha$ EW. Throughout the entire time plotted in Fig. D.3 (about 145 days), the Štefl frequency is evident, with the most obvious change being an increase in amplitude for about 10 days (starting at HJD 2450220) while the EW was numerically decreasing (emission strength was increasing). ω CMa is viewed at a low inclination angle, and had a roughly constant $H\alpha$ EW for the first 40 days plotted in Fig. D.4, and the emission strength (relative to the continuum) decreased in the last ~ 15 days. The Štefl frequency (here seen in the EW_V/EW_R) is obvious throughout this entire time, appealingly increasing in amplitude towards the end of this dataset. For both stars, the lower-right panels of Figs. D.3 and D.4 show the EW_V/EW_R measurements phased to their respective Štefl frequencies, demonstrating that these variations are consistent with a (near-)constant frequency and phase.

It is not entirely clear why η Cen and ω CMa have such long-lasting Štefl frequencies. Perhaps these systems exhibit more continuous mass ejection (but with variable rates of mass flux) compared to the short, punctuated events studied in this work. Given the very different viewing angles, this cannot be explained solely by a line-of-sight inclination angle effect.

Fig. D.2. Available TESS photometry for η Cen (left) and ω CMa (right). The bottom panels show the frequency content of the photometry for each plotted sector.

Fig. D.3. $H\alpha$ data for η Cen. *Top:* $H\alpha$ EW. *Middle:* $H\alpha$ EW_V/EW_R . *Bottom-left:* $H\alpha$ line profiles. *Bottom-right:* $H\alpha$ EW_V/EW_R phased to the circumstellar Štefl frequency. In all panels, the color changes with time from blue to red.

Fig. D.4. Same as Fig. D.3 but for ω CMa.

Appendix E: X-rays in V767 Cen

V767 Cen has been observed in X-rays several times notably in July 2021 – January 2022, when a simultaneous optical and X-ray monitoring was performed (Nazé et al. 2022a). At the time, the star was undergoing a several-year decreasing trend of its H α emission but a sudden emission strengthening appeared, marking the start of an outburst and of the X-ray campaign. The EW(H α) at the time of the X-ray observations ranged from around -4\AA for the exposure taken near peak emission value and -2\AA for exposures taken on the rising branch and at the end of the outburst. Despite a large change in H α , the recorded X-ray flux appeared remarkably stable considering errors ($\sigma \sim 12\%$), as was its hardness. Flux and hardness were also similar compared to a previous XMM-Newton observation taken in January 2007.

Taking advantage of the TESS campaign, an additional observation was taken with the Swift X-ray telescope on June 1st 2023 (HJD=2460097.016 or TJD=3097.016, ObsID=00014422009). This corresponds to the end of the TESS observations, and the photometric peak of an outburst - EW(H α) was around -3\AA at the time. The EW_V/EW_R cycles for this event were of low amplitude at the Swift epoch, indicating that the ejected material had nearly circularized.

As the source is rather bright at optical/UV wavelengths, the windowed timing mode was used, as it was before. The count rate and spectra were extracted using the on-line Swift tool^a. Swift count rates for this new observation amount to 0.116 ± 0.012 cts s⁻¹ in the 0.5–10. keV band, which is again in line with those recorded before ($0.07\text{--}0.12$ cts s⁻¹). The ratio between count rates in 2.–10. keV and 0.5–2.0 keV reaches 0.60 ± 0.13 while it was 0.31–0.67 before.

Spectral fitting was done as in Nazé et al. (2022), with an absorbed two-temperature model (kT fixed to 0.28 and 6.02 keV). The spectral parameters are $N_{\text{H}} = [0.043 + (0.05 \pm 0.11)] \times 10^{22}$ cm⁻² for the interstellar and circumstellar components, respectively, and $norm(6.02) = 0.00222 \pm 0.00031$ cm⁻⁵ (the normalization of the coolest component being fixed to 8% of that value). The observed flux in the 0.5–10. keV then amounts to $(3.72 \pm 0.51) \times 10^{-12}$ erg cm⁻² s⁻¹ and the hardness ratio, defined as the ratio between the fluxes in 2.–10. keV and 0.5–2.0 keV after correction for the interstellar absorption, is 1.78 ± 0.32 . Again, all those values appear similar to those recorded before, demonstrating the absence of drastic changes and a rather constant character for the long-term X-ray emission of V767 Cen.

Subtle and fast responses could however not be probed. The previous Swift data indicated possible hints of a larger luminosity and hardness closer to the start of an event, but those were only 1 sigma variations: clearly, more sensitive X-ray data taken very swiftly after the start of an outburst would provide further indications of the exact X-ray impact of such events.

^a https://www.swift.ac.uk/user_objects/ - calibration available on Nov. 12 2024